

Euro-optimism Intertwined with Pragmatism: Elite and Popular Discourses on Georgia's Europeanization through Q Methodology

Abstract

The paper discusses Georgia's political and intellectual elites' and citizens' discourses on the country's Europeanization in the context of pragmatic and identity considerations. The research is based on Q methodology that, in contrast to its traditional use, has been integrated into in-depth interviews with political and intellectual elites and focus group discussions with citizens residing in the urban areas of Georgia. Q analysis has revealed that both elites and citizens are characterized by Euro-optimistic views perceiving Georgia's Europeanization in light of pragmatic considerations. The major pragmatic factors are related to the improved protection of human rights and the safeguarding of the country's security. Unlike previous studies, the current research has shown that, at least at the rhetorical level, Georgia's Europeanization is not perceived as a threat to the national identity.

Keywords: Europeanization; Georgia; elites; citizens; pragmatic factors; national identity

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Introduction

When we visit the official website of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Georgia, statements such as the one by David Zalkaliani, the former Minister of Foreign Affairs, instantly attract our attention: “Common European values determine the Georgian people’s resolute will to become a full-fledged member of the European family” (9 May 2020). It is quite usual for high officials in Georgia to refer to “common European values” as a justification of the country’s European path and this tradition has firmly established itself since the Rose Revolution of 2003. Indeed, since around that date, Georgia made European integration its foreign policy priority and the new political elite started rebranding the country’s image to underline its European identity instead of the Caucasian one (Emerson 2004). Georgia’s aspiration to get closer to the “European family” was represented as an inevitable trajectory of the country’s development and modernization (De Waal 2011) that resulted in the signing of the European Union (EU)–Georgia Association Agreement in 2014. Furthermore, as illustrated by the Caucasus Research Resource Center (CRRC) Georgia’s biennial nationwide surveys on “Knowledge of and Attitudes Toward the EU in Georgia” (2009–21), the country has been steadily characterized by highly pro-European attitudes, with more than two-thirds of the population supporting its European integration. Despite this positive outlook, Georgia still faces a characteristic dilemma of small and peripheral aspirant states that is referred to elsewhere as an “integration dilemma” (Kelstrup 1992, 154): they try not to be excluded from the integration process though are also concerned about certain transformations caused by it. As shown by former research on Georgia’s Europeanization (Tsuladze et al. 2016, Tsuladze, Esebua and Osepashvili 2021, Tsuladze 2021), the above dilemma is triggered by an interplay between pragmatic and identity considerations stemming from the country’s Europeanization.

The current paper offers a new insight into Georgians’ perceptions of such pragmatic and identity factors and, by doing so, contributes to the sociological study of Georgia’s European integration and Europeanization. Although sociology identified its focus in the Europeanization research (Jacquot and Woll 2003) at the same time as international relations and political science defined theirs,¹ the contribution of sociology to the field has been rather marginal. In contrast to international relations and political science, which view Europeanization as a process of “adaptation” focusing on the transformation of local norms

¹ For instance, Schimmelfennig and Sedelmeier theorized EU enlargement (2002), and Radaelli offered his famous definition of Europeanization (2003).

and standards in the course of European integration (Radaelli 2003), sociology is interested in the “usage of European integration” with a special focus on its discursive aspect (Jacquot and Woll 2003). It is through this discursive usage that “different constructions and images of Europe” are formed and “constantly re-negotiated and co-constructed by different elites and social groups” (Wodak and Weiss 2005, 128), and hence different versions of Europe and the EU are invented (Delanty 1995). These constructions and images are a means of legitimizing certain EU practices or depriving them of legitimacy (Radaelli 2003).

Wodak and Weiss identify “three forms of legitimizing the political construction of the EU (and its enlargement)”: “legitimization through idea (identity, history, culture), legitimization through procedure (participation, democracy, efficiency), and legitimization through ‘standardization’ (of social standards, economic standards)” (2005, 131). The first form of legitimization, which refers to the idea of Europe and focuses on the identity and cultural dimensions, fosters the *value-based* or *identity* approach to the EU, with its emphasis on the ascribed and achieved aspects of national and supranational attachment. The other two forms legitimize or delegitimize the EU based on the *rational utilitarian* or *pragmatic* views, related to the perception of gains or losses stemming from Europeanization. The latter can be related to the strengthening of democratic institutions or economic benefits of the free trade area vis-à-vis certain political drawbacks or possible economic costs (Toshkov et al. 2014). Thus, the identity and pragmatic factors are discursively used for the legitimization or delegitimization of the EU and the European project, and can be manipulated by elites and various social groups. Therefore, it is important to study the discursive usage of Europeanization at the level of both elites and citizens.

Analysing the role of discourse in any socio-political setting, scholars identify two types of discourse: coordinative discourse, implying the exchange of ideas among those responsible for policy construction, and communicative discourse, a top-down shaping of national political understandings reflected in popular perceptions (Schmidt and Radaelli 2004, 196). While addressing these discourses, it is inevitable that we discuss both elites’ and citizens’ perceptions of pragmatic and identity considerations related to their country’s Europeanization. Following this idea, the present paper focuses on the representations of pragmatic and identity factors in the elite and popular discourses on Europeanization in Georgia to reveal how they are discursively used to legitimize or delegitimize the Europeanization process. For this purpose, the paper first outlines the role of pragmatic and identity factors in shaping elite and popular discourses on Europeanization. In order to create a context for the Georgian case, it focuses on the Eastern enlargement countries that

underwent the process of European integration in the recent past. Then the research method – Q methodology – is presented, which has been innovatively applied in the course of the current research. Finally, Georgian elites’ and citizens’ perceptions of the pragmatic and identity considerations related to the country’s Europeanization are discussed.

Role of Pragmatic and Identity Factors in Shaping Attitudes toward the EU

As noted in the introduction, two major factors are identified that influence political action and public opinion toward the European project and Europeanization: the rational utilitarian or pragmatic and the value-based or identity factors. The pragmatic framework relates to collective and individual benefits associated with the EU in terms of economic development and education, as well as proper functioning of political institutions and protection of human rights (della Porta and Caiani 2009). In many cases, a security agenda becomes an important element of this list (Delanty 1995; Tsuladze 2021). The identity framework relates to the perceived cultural threats and respective identity concerns stemming from a country’s European integration (Hooghe and Marks 2005, 2008; McLaren 2002, 2007; Karp and Bowler 2006), as the latter obviously contributes to the redefinition of national identity.

However, it should be underlined that pragmatic and identity considerations might be closely intertwined and their categorization as belonging to a certain framework might be shaped by their use in a particular context. For instance, protection of human rights as a means of reinforcing democracy is considered one of the major pragmatic gains stemming from the Europeanization process. However, it might also trigger the discourse of tolerance, which represents tolerance as a national characteristic in aspirant countries like Georgia. Based on empirical data, the discourse of Georgians’ “historic” or “inborn” tolerance as an indicator of their European identity has become one of the key arguments in relation to the idea of Georgia’s return to its “European family” (Tsuladze et al. 2016; Tsuladze, Esebua and Osepashvili 2021). The same is true about security considerations that can be viewed in a pragmatic light of enhanced territorial defence though they can also be represented as vital for safeguarding national or European identity (Matonyte and Morkevicius 2012).

Recent studies have revealed that various dimensions influencing attitudes toward the EU and European integration either can be aggregated in the identity and pragmatic factors or are closely interlinked with them. For instance, in 2011, scholars proposed five dimensions of EU attitudes: “(1) EU effect, referring to feelings of fear of and threat by the EU, (2) a sense of European identity, (3) the performance and democratic functioning of the EU and its institutions, (4) utilitarian considerations, and (5) a strengthening of the EU”, which have

been tested in a later piece of research targeting twenty-one countries (de Vreese, Azrout and Boomgaarden 2019, 195). No doubt, the first two dimensions represent identity considerations (the EU's impact on (1) national and (2) supranational identities), the fourth dimension includes various pragmatic considerations, while the remaining ones refer to the effective functioning of the EU itself, which has a significant impact on the perceptions of certain benefits stemming from European integration or the EU's influence on local identity. The research aiming to test the five-dimensional model has confirmed its relevance in all twenty-one countries, although in some countries it demonstrates a better fit than in others. The countries with the best fit are the ones in Eastern and Central Europe. In contrast to expectations, the research has shown that longer membership and participation in the common currency do not translate into a better fit. Furthermore, the level of EU investment and economic ties between EU member states do not matter for the dimensional structure either (ibid., 209). Considering that the model holds especially well in the EU's new member states, it is interesting to find out what makes it fit better in the context of Eastern enlargement countries that have achieved the goal Georgia ambitiously attempts to achieve.

The existing body of research reveals that although the factors affecting the attitudes toward the EU in the old and new EU member states do not differ, their prioritization is still different. In contrast to the old member states, the citizens of new member states do not expect immediate economic gains from European integration but rather certain benefits in terms of new opportunities and better functioning of democratic institutions (Doyle and Fidrmuc 2006, 541). Thus, the long-term democratic gains associated with European integration prevail over the short-term economic ones in the Eastern enlargement countries. Another important difference between the old and new members is their perception of security issues. A considerably larger portion of elites of the post-communist Central and Eastern European countries (60 per cent) view Russia as a security threat to Europe than those of Western European countries (30 per cent). Such a discrepancy can be explained by the post-communist countries' historical experience and territorial proximity with Russia (Matonyte and Morkevicius 2012, 103–4). Thus, it can be argued that, for the new member states (as well as the EU-associated ones that also represent the post-communist countries bordering Russia), the security and democracy agenda overshadows economic interests in the process of European integration. In the empirical part of the paper I will show that in line with the above data and in contrast to the studies that view identity considerations as key to Georgians' perceptions of European integration (Gvalia et al. 2013; German 2015; Kakachia and Minesashvili 2015), the pragmatic considerations related to democracy and security are

major factors affecting Georgian elites' and citizens' perceptions of the country's European integration and Europeanization.

Furthermore, evidence shows that elites and population expect different advantages and disadvantages related to European integration. The key difference between the positions of elites and population is “the empowerment or loss of control that collective actors attribute to a transfer of national responsibilities and authority to the European level” (Best 2012, 240), and hence the perceived threats to national sovereignty as well as national identity. Indeed, as the section on data analysis illustrates, in Georgians' perceptions, the national sovereignty and national identity considerations are closely intertwined, and although elites and the younger generation view European integration as harmful to neither the former nor the latter, certain concerns still surface in older citizens' discourses. It is assumed that the rise of similar concerns among the citizens of EU member states caused the shift from “permissive consensus” to “constraining dissensus” in public support for European integration (Hooghe and Marks 2008). Although this trend was already visible by the time of Eastern enlargement among the old EU member states, for quite a while the portion of those supporting European integration and generally having a positive image of the EU was still higher owing to the Euro-optimistic attitudes of Eastern Europeans, which started declining around 2010. However, the Spring 2019 Standard Eurobarometer showed a sudden shift in this tendency, revealing that the portion of citizens with a positive image of the EU increased in twenty-three EU member states and this upward trend has further continued, as illustrated by the Standard Eurobarometer of June–July 2021 (European Commission, 10 September 2021).

What factors are considered decisive for such shifts in EU-supportive attitudes? There are a number of individual- and collective-level factors to be taken into account. The most significant demographic and socio-economic factors affecting citizens' views of the EU are their age, education, employment status and economic wellbeing. Evidence shows that younger age, higher education and higher income positively correlate with EU-supportive attitudes, while unemployment and residence in rural areas work the other way around (Toshkov et al. 2014; Pew Research Center 2019; European Commission 2010–2018; CRRC Georgia 2009–2021). Furthermore, studies reveal that attitudes toward the EU are significantly influenced by a local political context (especially, local political actors' performance at the national and EU levels, as well as citizens' attitudes toward national governments and parliaments) and not the EU itself (Dimitrov, Harlampiev and Stoychev 2015, 14–18). Consequently, citizens' political affiliation and their awareness of EU-related

themes vis-à-vis local events are crucial for the formation of their respective attitudes (Boomgaarden et al. 2011; de Vreese and Boomgaarden 2005; Hooghe and Marks 2005; Karp and Bowler 2006).

Studies also show that the citizens of Eastern enlargement countries have gradually developed more realistic (in terms of the pace and timing of Europeanization) views about the European project, which contributes to the weakening of sentiments related to the symbolic ties to the EU. Based on this trend, scholars underline the recent shift from a more superficial, Euro-enthusiastic discourse to a more pragmatic one in the new member states, which results in the shift from the initial Euro-optimistic views to the Euro-realistic and at times even Eurosceptic ones at both the public and elite levels (Heinisch and Landsberger 2011). Considering the abovementioned trend, it is important to find out whether Georgian elites' and citizens' discourses about the EU and European integration reveal the same dynamics as those of their forerunners and whether there has been a shift from more Euro-enthusiastic views to the pragmatic ones in the Georgian reality. As I will show in the following subsections, Euro-optimism and pragmatism are closely intertwined in Georgian elites' and citizens' views. Moreover, it is the anticipation of pragmatic gains that encourages optimistic perceptions of the country's European integration and Europeanization. Before presenting the research findings, I will provide a detailed description of the research method – namely, Q methodology – that has been innovatively applied in the current research.

Research Method

The present research is based on methodological triangulation integrating qualitative and quantitative approaches.² The target group is represented by, on the one hand, political elites – in particular, the parliamentary majority (Georgian Dream) and the largest parliamentary minority (United National Movement), as well as government officials (none of the political actors known for their anti-EU or pro-Russian sentiments agreed to participate in the research)³ – and on the other hand, intellectual elites (the academic community and civil

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³ Based on our experience of studying political actors’ discourses on Europeanization in Georgia, representatives of political parties with anti-European sentiments (that often coincide with pro-Russian ones) usually refuse to participate in the research. The main reason is probably the fact that, in order not to irritate the public, they avoid

society/non-governmental organization (NGO) sector). Besides political and intellectual elites, the target group also consists of citizens residing in the urban areas of Georgia. In the course of research, thirty-one in-depth interviews were conducted with the representatives of political and intellectual elites, and eighteen focus group discussions were held with the population in three major cities of Eastern Georgia (Tbilisi, Gori and Telavi) and three major cities of Western Georgia (Kutaisi, Zugdidi and Batumi). As the CRRC Georgia surveys on “Knowledge of and Attitudes Toward the EU in Georgia” (2009–19) showed that younger age and higher education positively correlated with pro-European attitudes, the population was divided into three age groups that also matched their socialization in the Soviet and post-Soviet periods. The groups consisted of those aged 18–25, who were socialized in the post-Soviet period; those aged 26–40, who were socialized partially in the Soviet and partially in the post-Soviet times; and finally, those aged 41–65, who were socialized in the Soviet period. Overall, there was an equal distribution of males and females in the focus groups, while those with higher education represented two-thirds of the research participants. Three focus groups were held with the abovementioned age groups in each target city involving 137 participants.

Q methodology was integrated in the course of both in-depth interviews with elites and focus group discussions with citizens. Despite its quantitative focus, Q methodology is used with rather small samples, allowing a deeper analysis of individual cases (McKeown and Thomas 2013). In the course of research, the research participants are provided with pre-formulated statements that are placed on a Q grid, based on the respondents’ views of their importance/unimportance and, concurrently, their agreement/disagreement with them. A limited number of cells in a Q grid makes the respondents select the most prioritized statements, while the least prioritized ones are left for the neutral category.

Q methodology implies four stages of data analysis: correlation analysis, factor analysis, factor rotation, and calculation of factor scores (Z-scores). Based on correlation analysis, consensus–dissensus is measured between two categories of variables assessed on a scale from +1 to –1. As a result, a correlation matrix involving all Q columns (Q sorts) is developed that shows similarities and differences between the respondents’ views. At the next stage, the major factors are identified in the abovementioned matrix and all the factors with a value above 1 are selected for factor rotation (eigenvalues point to the validity of

openly criticizing the country’s foreign policy course, that is, European integration. They also avoid overtly expressing their pro-Russian sentiments.

factors and are considered significant if they are above 1), upon which the most important factors are grouped to enable better interpretation. The major factors identified have an explanatory power if they account for up to 50 per cent of the research findings. Finally, Z-score variance is measured showing the value of each statement within each factor, as well as the consensus–dissensus among factors (Watts and Stenner 2012).

In order to develop a Q grid for the current research, we referred to our former study entitled “Performing Europeanization – Political vis-à-vis Popular Discourses on Europeanization in Georgia” (Tsuladze et al. 2016), which analysed the respective discourses after Georgia signed the Association Agreement with the EU. All key political and popular discourses related to Georgia’s Europeanization were selected from this research and resulted in around 100 statements, which were further given to the experts working on various aspects of Georgia’s European integration to shortlist the most relevant statements in the present conditions. Ultimately, a list of thirty statements was developed for the current research and the respondents were asked to place the statements in the Q grid’s relevant cells, based on their own vision of their importance (whether it was viewed in a positive or negative light), as well as to explain their rationale for such a distribution of statements. As limited time would not allow the respondents to comment on the placement of all the statements, they explained the reasoning behind the ultimate positive and negative poles consisting of the fewest number of cells (+3/–3 and +2/–2). We also asked the respondents follow-up questions to enrich the provided explanations with additional details. After the data were collected, the abovementioned four stages of data analysis were performed using the Ken-Q Analysis online software.⁴

The applied approach is innovative in that Q methodology has not been used in the Europeanization research in Georgia before. Furthermore, the scholars using Q methodology do not enquire for underlying assumptions beyond the offered discourses and the participants are simply asked to place the statements on the Q grid provided. Thus, a traditional application of Q methodology neither envisions participants’ explanations nor asks follow-up questions, while a further step has been taken in the present research to combine quantitative and qualitative approaches creatively. The participants’ explanations of the rationale for placing the statements in a particular way and their reflections on the special importance of certain statements provided rich and comprehensive data that were analysed qualitatively.

⁴ Ken-Q Analysis, version 0.11.1 (January 15, 2018): <https://shawnbanasick.github.io/ken-q-analysis-beta/index.html#section1>.

Thus, the integration of Q methodology with in-depth interviews and focus groups has enabled a special insight into the subject matter.

The current paper focuses on Q analysis, while the qualitative data are used only for the purpose of clarification. As a few recent papers by the author and her team (Tsuladze, Esebua and Osepashvili 2021; Tsuladze 2021; Tsuladze and Osepashvili 2021) provide a detailed analysis of respective qualitative findings, this time the decision has been made to focus on Q methodology and its application in the Europeanization research. Because the present paper targets the perceptions of pragmatic and identity factors related to Georgia’s Europeanization, for the purpose of illustration, out of the thirty Q statements that relate to various aspects of Georgia’s Europeanization only those reflecting pragmatic and identity concerns most widespread among Georgians are presented in Table 1. The statements have both positive and negative formulations in order to avoid the respondents’ following of certain response patterns. In addition, despite offering similar statements to elites and citizens, the wording was somewhat simplified for the latter.

<i>Q statements related to pragmatic factors that research participants most often referred to</i>	<i>Q statements related to identity factors that research participants most often referred to</i>
a. Alongside European integration human rights will be much better protected in Georgia	g. The dissemination of European values is harmful to Georgian traditions
b. Georgia cannot independently confront Russian threats and hence it is important for the country to integrate with the “European family”	h. The Georgian Orthodox Church represents an obstacle on the way to the country’s Europeanization
c. In the process of European integration, Georgia has to implement rather painful reforms, though it is necessary for the country’s wellbeing	i. Alongside the dissemination of European liberal values Georgians become more tolerant
d. If Georgia persistently implements EU regulations, one day it will inevitably become an EU member state	j. Georgia has been historically tolerant and does not need to be taught tolerance by the EU

e. Georgian products cannot really establish on the European market, as they are not able to compete with European products	k. Despite Georgia’s pro-European course, it is important to maintain friendly relations with Russia because of sharing a common history and religion
f. Alongside European integration the Georgian government will not be able to make independent decisions and the country’s sovereignty will weaken	l. The Georgian government should follow EU standards and ensure the protection of rights of sexual minorities even if the majority of population is against it

Table 1. Q statements.

In line with the above argument that pragmatic and identity factors are defined by their use in a particular context, the last statement that has to do with the protection of human rights can be considered an inseparable part of the identity discourse. Based on the existing studies, the main identity threat envisaged by Georgia’s population as an outcome of European integration is the dissemination of homosexual relations that is viewed as harmful to Georgian family traditions and identity (Tsuladze et al. 2016; Tsuladze, Esebua and Osepashvili 2021).

In what follows, I will discuss the main findings regarding the elites’ and citizens’ perceptions of pragmatic and identity factors related to Georgia’s Europeanization focusing on the major trends revealed on the basis of Q analysis.

Euro-optimism Intertwined with Pragmatism: Political and Intellectual Elites’ Views

Based on Q analysis, political and intellectual elites’ views can be grouped in five major factors that account for 65 per cent of the research findings. Among them, the leading one is Factor 1, accounting for 43 per cent of the findings and representing the pragmatic expectations related to Georgia’s European integration. The validity of Factor 1 is visible from its eigenvalue, which is very high (13). The other four factors jointly account for 22 per cent of the research findings and their eigenvalues vary from 1.5 to 2.

Although Factor 1 comprises various elites, its core is represented by the parliamentary majority and minority (hence it can be labelled “Politician”), while NGO representatives make the core of Factors 4 and 5, in which the pragmatic perceptions of the EU are also dominant (hence these factors can be labelled “NGO 1” and “NGO 2”, respectively). The other two factors are rather heterogeneous, consisting of government

officials, NGO representatives and the academic community. Factor score correlations show that Factor “Politician” strongly correlates with Factor “NGO 2”, which is a rather unexpected result. However, the statements aggregated within these two factors are quite similar: namely, in both cases the statements at the ultimate positive pole relate to the expected benefits of Georgia’s Europeanization, while the ones at the ultimate negative pole represent the perceived threats to the national identity. Thus, we can conclude that the MPs’ and NGO representatives’ views coincide in both their assessment of the benefits stemming from European integration and in the fact that neither of these groups perceives Europeanization as a threat to national traditions and identity. Considering the pragmatic factor loading, it can be argued that the anticipated instrumental gains determine Georgian political and intellectual elites’ assessments of the country’s Europeanization.

As regards the contents of Factor “Politician”, the ultimate positive pole is represented by the following two statements: “Georgia cannot independently confront Russian threats and hence it is important for the country to integrate with the ‘European family’” and “Alongside European integration human rights will be much better protected in Georgia.” The latter statement strongly correlates with the following one: “The government should follow EU standards and ensure the protection of rights of sexual minorities even if the majority of population is against it.” It can be argued that in the given context pragmatic and identity considerations are intertwined. As the follow-up discussions show, on the one hand, the pragmatic need of reinforcing human rights for the better functioning of Georgia’s democracy is underlined, while on the other hand, a new discourse is introduced, which attempts to “normalize” homosexual relations and refute a widespread argument that they might harm Georgian family traditions. Furthermore, as both the follow-up discussions and factor correlations show, pragmatic gains related to democracy and security are also viewed as closely interlinked and the improvement of the country’s democratic performance is considered a means of countering Russian threats.

Two more statements have significant values in Factor “Politician”: “If Georgia persistently implements EU regulations, one day it will inevitably become an EU member state” and “Euro-Atlantic integration is the choice of the Georgian people and not of political elites.” No doubt, both statements are used by MPs for their socially desirable performance: the first, Euro-optimistic one is meant to underline the governing elite’s belief that its attempts will be surely rewarded by the EU via offering Georgia membership. At the same time, it is beneficial for both the parliamentary majority (that signed the EU–Georgia Association Agreement) and the largest parliamentary minority (that, at the time of

representing the governing party, made European integration Georgia's foreign policy priority) to state that Euro-Atlantic integration is the choice of the Georgian people and not of political elites. This strategy enables each party to avoid the acknowledgement of its political opponent's contribution to the country's European path.

The following two statements comprise the ultimate negative pole in Factor "Politician": "The dissemination of European values is harmful to Georgian traditions" and "Alongside European integration the Georgian government will not be able to make independent decisions and the country's sovereignty will weaken." Thus, political elites do not seem to envisage any threats to national values, neither to the country's sovereignty, alongside Georgia's Europeanization. Furthermore, a strong correlation between the two statements confirms that the identity and sovereignty aspects are perceived as closely interlinked. The follow-up discussions reveal that the identity discourse offered by MPs underlines Georgians' European identity with the research participants stressing that Georgia "naturally" belongs to the European family. Georgians' "historical aspiration to be European" (MP, parliamentary majority) is considered one of the main reasons for their belonging to the European family. This historical aspiration is believed to be reinforced by common Christian values. Furthermore, one of the indicators of Georgians' European identity is considered to be their "inborn tolerance", which, in the participants' words, points to the fact that the same virtues are valued in Europe and Georgia. Representing European values as harmful to the Georgian identity and likewise depicting the EU's normative power as a threat to the country's sovereignty are believed to be part of the anti-European propaganda disseminated by Russia (MP, parliamentary minority).

Factors "NGO 1" and "NGO 2" are both characterized by Euro-optimistic views intertwined with pragmatism. As the statements on the importance of European integration for both safeguarding Georgia against Russian threats and ensuring a better protection of human rights have significant values in all five factors, we can argue that they represent key statements in the political and intellectual elites' Q grids. Two statements have the highest positive scores in Factor "NGO 2" that shows the strongest correlation with Factor "Politician": "Georgia cannot independently confront Russian threats and hence it is important for the country to integrate with the 'European family'" and "In the process of European integration, Georgia has to implement rather painful reforms, though it is necessary for the country's wellbeing." That the implementation of "painful reforms" is expected to be rewarded by the EU is evident from the intellectual elites' belief that "If Georgia persistently implements EU regulations, one day it will inevitably become an EU member state." Thus,

two important benefits stemming from the country's Europeanization are considered to be its enhanced security and its acquisition of membership perspective.

In addition, there are also optimistic views regarding the impact of European values on the national identity, evidenced by the intellectual elites' agreement with the statement that "Alongside the dissemination of European liberal values Georgians become more tolerant," as well as their disagreement with the statement that "The dissemination of European values is harmful to Georgian traditions." In this context, we can again observe a close interconnection between identity and pragmatic considerations, which is confirmed by the follow-up discussions: The EU is depicted as an actor reinforcing democracy in Georgia through supporting a better protection of human rights that, on its side, invigorates Georgians' "historic" tolerance and reactivates the discourse of Georgia's return to its European family. Based on this line of thought, it can be argued that perceptions of the pragmatic gains stemming from the country's Europeanization also contribute to the reinforcement of respective identity discourse.

However, in contrast to political elites, intellectual elites explicitly disagree on the statement that "Despite Georgia's pro-European course, it is important to maintain friendly relations with Russia because of sharing a common history and religion." In this respect, political elites, particularly those from the ruling party, are rather diplomatic and try to avoid commenting on this issue, placing the above statement closer to the neutral category; while in the follow-up discussions they assess their own strategy as aiming to "not irritate Russia." Another statement that occupies a negative pole in both factors dominated by NGO representatives is the following one: "Georgia would have implemented the ongoing reforms even without the EU's demands as it is necessary for the country's modernization." In fact, this topic caused an animated discussion, with NGO representatives stating that the authorities implement the ongoing reforms merely because it is their obligation under the Association Agreement. Although the government is aware that these reforms are beneficial to the citizens, it does not willingly implement them but rather "stretches in time". The participants argue that the main reason for such a delay is the government's attempt to avoid public criticism by attributing rather "painful" reforms to the EU's directives, which ultimately portrays the EU as a powerful actor interfering in Georgia's internal affairs. The NGO representatives criticize the government for being aware of the harmful effects of this rhetoric though still using it as a "topoi" strategy, to use Wodak's term. The latter implies a "seemingly convincing fallacious argument" (Wodak 2011, 529) that blames current issues on someone else without providing respective evidence.

One more actor whose role in the process of European integration NGO representatives critically assess is the Georgian Orthodox Church. This is confirmed by a strong agreement with the statement that “The Georgian Orthodox Church represents an obstacle on the way to the country’s Europeanization” in Factor “NGO 1” (it should be underlined that, in contrast to NGO representatives, MPs and government officials offer a rather careful position and tend to express either a neutral position or a mild disagreement with this statement, which is another example of their manipulative strategy). Only two local actors deserve NGO representatives’ positive assessment in the process of Georgia’s Europeanization, namely, the younger generation and the NGO sector itself.

To summarize the major trends revealed on the basis of political and intellectual elites’ views, they mainly expect pragmatic gains related to democratization and securitization from Georgia’s European integration. Furthermore, they do not envisage any identity threats stemming from the country’s Europeanization. It is also evident that at times pragmatic and identity discourses are closely intertwined and the former can activate the latter, as in the case of perceived pragmatic gains related to the improved protection of human rights, which triggers the discourse of Georgians’ “inborn” or “historic” tolerance as an indicator of their European identity. Despite these similarities, there are also visible differences between political and intellectual elites’ assessments: Intellectual elites reject any possibility of Georgia’s maintaining friendly relations with Russia alongside European integration, while political elites, particularly those from the ruling party, masterfully avoid discussing this question. Intellectual elites consider the Georgian Orthodox Church an impediment on the way to the country’s Europeanization, while political elites avoid discussing this question either. Intellectual elites directly state that if it were not for EU pressure, no reforms would be implemented in Georgia, while the ruling party representatives are especially manipulative in this context: On the one hand, they state that the ongoing reforms would have been implemented even without the EU’s demands, as these reforms are necessary for the country’s modernization, while on the other hand, they think the ongoing reforms are dictated by the EU, which results in their use of the “topoi” strategy.

Such a discursive manipulation is vividly reflected in the follow-up discussions, which reveal that the ruling party representatives assess the implementation of EU reforms as both valuable and risky, and this contradictory view might even be voiced by the same respondent within the same narrative. One of the most vivid examples is the following excerpt: “We do not do it only because the EU wants us to do so but because these reforms are valuable. [...] The EU’s demands simply accelerate certain things. You might not dare to

take a risk and the EU pushes you, so to speak” (MP, parliamentary majority). It is obvious that the EU’s role in pushing the reforms in Georgia is acknowledged even in the first sentence noting that not *only* the EU’s demands are important but also the Georgian policymakers’ awareness, though the latter still does not change the perception of reforms as risky. In this complex situation, the need for a reform to be dictated is both rejected and recognized, which results in quite ambivalent discourses on Georgia’s Europeanization (discussed in detail in Tsuladze and Osepashvili 2021). The same ambivalence has been revealed in the former research on Georgians’ political and popular discourses on Europeanization, which has shown that EU regulations are declared an “enforced” mechanism that Georgia should “voluntarily” implement in order to become an EU member state (Tsuladze et al. 2016). It should also be noted that political elites do acknowledge the performative character of their own rhetoric and agree with the statement that “In order to ensure the population’s support, the majority of Georgian politicians try to stage a pro-European performance” (surprisingly, political elites tend to agree with this statement more than intellectual elites do).

Euro-optimism Intertwined with Pragmatism: Citizens’ Views

Based on Q analysis, citizens’ views can be grouped in six major factors that account for 55 per cent of the research findings. The key one is Factor 1, whose content is similar to that of the first factor identified among political and intellectual elites, with the focus on pragmatic expectations related to Georgia’s European integration. This factor accounts for 29 per cent of the research findings, while other five factors jointly account for 26 per cent. Eigenvalues are remarkably high for all six factors, exceeding the value of 10 for Factor 1 and varying from 5 to 9 in the case of the other five factors. Factor score correlations reveal that there is the strongest positive correlation between Factors 1 and 4 (both express a Euro-optimistic position intertwined with pragmatism). Out of the six factors, Factor 6 is the only Eurosceptic one.

Factor 1 is mainly represented by the youngest participants (aged 18–25) residing in the capital city of Tbilisi, as well as those aged 26–40 residing in Tbilisi and Western Georgia (hence it can be labelled “Those under 40”). As noted above, the main focus of this factor matches that of Factor “Politician”: in particular, the ultimate positive pole is represented by the statements related to the instrumental gains stemming from the country’s European integration, while the ultimate negative pole is represented by the statement related to the EU’s harmful effects on national traditions and identity. In this respect, the current research

findings differ from those of the earlier research, which revealed that citizens were quite concerned about the identity threats ascribed to the country's European integration (Tsuladze et al. 2016). Furthermore, as illustrated by CRRC Georgia surveys on "Knowledge of and Attitudes Toward the EU in Georgia" (2009–15), a considerable portion of Georgia's population perceived European integration as harmful to national traditions. However, as the later surveys showed, the portion of those fearing this harmful effect steadily decreased from 45 per cent in 2015 to 17 per cent in 2019 (CRRC Georgia 2019). Besides, it is important to note that Factor "Those under 40" is mainly represented by young people residing in the capital, who, according to the CRRC surveys, are better informed about EU-related topics and are less concerned about the loss of national identity than the older generation or those residing in the regions. Finally, the latest data demonstrate that residents of the capital, more often than the rest of the population, identify the goal of joining the EU as the country's major priority, while they view the protection of human rights as one of the main benefits stemming from the EU (CRRC Georgia 2021).

Q analysis also confirms that in terms of pragmatic expectations related to the country's European integration, similar to political and intellectual elites, citizens envisage better protection of human rights and the safeguarding of Georgia against Russian threats. In fact, the same two statements have the highest positive values in Factor "Those under 40" as in Factor "Politician." Furthermore, the research participants express a Euro-optimistic view that as a result of persistently implementing EU reforms, one day Georgia will be granted a member status. Although they argue that much effort is still needed to succeed with the country's modernization, they believe that certain changes have been introduced with the EU's support exemplified by a widespread recognition of the need for protection of human rights. Thus, certain pragmatic gains stemming from the country's Europeanization are considered already visible. However, the young participants believe that despite these positive changes, without the EU's pressure the government would not have implemented the current reforms. Finally, they underline the distinction between younger and older generations' views and think that "Young people are more supportive of Georgia's European integration than the generation raised in the Soviet period."

As in the case of elites, the perceived identity concerns occupy the ultimate negative pole, especially the statement that "The dissemination of European values is harmful to Georgian traditions." One more statement young people disagree with is that "Despite Georgia's pro-European course, it is important to maintain friendly relations with Russia because of sharing a common history and religion." Thus, when it comes to identity

considerations, Factor “Those under 40” confirms that, in terms of common values and traditions, young people see Georgia as having closer ties with Europe than with Russia. This was especially evident in the course of follow-up discussions, with the participants’ discourses stressing Georgia’s historical Europeanness and perceiving Russia as its main impediment: “Georgians possess this inner Europeanness. [...] We certainly had this back in 1918–1921 [the period of Georgia’s first independent republic] and then Russia caused our stagnation” (male, 18–25, Tbilisi). This “inner Europeanness” is ascribed the same features as elites attribute to Georgians’ European identity, especially common Christian values and Georgians’ aspiration towards modernization. Thus, as in the case of politicians’ discourse on Georgians’ “inborn tolerance” and NGO representatives’ discourse on Georgians’ “historic tolerance”, the young people’s discourse on Georgians’ “inner Europeanness” is used as one of the main discursive strategies for legitimization of the country’s Europeanization.

At first sight, Factor 2, comprised primarily of older participants (aged 41–65) from the capital city and Eastern Georgia (hence it can be labelled “Those over 40”), also reflects the citizens’ Euro-optimistic views. However, a detailed analysis reveals a rather ambivalent vision. On the one hand, the EU is perceived as a “teacher” and it is believed that following its instructions will necessarily result in Georgia’s EU membership; concurrently, Euro-Atlantic integration is considered the choice of Georgian people and not of political elites, which leads us to the assumption that the dissemination of European values is not perceived as harmful to Georgian traditions (which is actually the case). However, on the other hand, certain ambivalence is invoked by the participants’ belief that when it comes to the issues related to sexual minorities, the Georgian government should take into account the population’s rather than the EU’s position. Such a vision confirms that although older citizens do not regard Europeanization as a threat to the national identity, non-heterosexual relations viewed as endorsed by the EU remain one of the most sensitive topics. Evidence shows that it is also one of the main themes of the right-wing groups’ (such as “The Georgian March” or “The Society for Protection of Children’s Rights”) discursive manipulation while spreading their messages against Georgia’s Europeanization. In fact, they reverse the argument about the improved protection of human rights as a result of the country’s Europeanization, concurrently depicting the latter as a threat to the Georgian identity: Europeanization as violating the rights of heterosexuals and children, and hence threatening traditional Georgian values. This is another example of pragmatic factor contributing to the reinforcement of identity discourse.

As for the perception of Russia-Georgia relations, it is noteworthy that the ultimate positive pole in Factor “Those over 40” is represented by the statement that, despite Georgia’s pro-European course, it is important to maintain friendly relations with Russia. Although the original statement emphasizes the two countries’ “common history and religion”, the follow-up discussions among older participants took a different direction (this time shifting from identity to pragmatic considerations) and resulted in the animated debates on what these “friendly” relations might mean. The research has revealed that, for the majority of participants who call Russia an occupier, “friendship” with Russia implies a careful diplomatic approach that will enable Georgia to counterbalance Russian power with clever manoeuvring. Considering that Georgia is a small and marginal country without an immediate border with the EU but having one with Russia, older participants are especially cautious of not aggravating the country’s relations with its northern neighbour: “We represent a small country. [...] Who is going to protect us? In the conditions when Russia has occupied and still occupies our territories, who has helped us?” (male, 41–65, Tbilisi). Overall, it seems the older generation is rather wary of adopting EU standards and is also more inclined towards maintaining friendly relations with Russia (even if this is dictated by the aspiration to prevent further occupation of Georgia’s territories), which is negatively assessed by young people. Despite this, older participants disagree with the statement that “Young people are more supportive of Georgia’s European integration than the generation raised in the Soviet period.”

Another actor invoking the population’s careful diplomatic approach is the Georgian Orthodox Church. The focus group participants of all age groups from all the regions place the statement “The Georgian Orthodox Church represents an obstacle on the way to the country’s Europeanization” in or close to the neutral category. This does not mean that they do not have a clear position in this respect but they try to avoid discussing this question. However, as illustrated by the follow-up comments, a number of participants, especially those representing the youngest age group, are rather critical about the church’s involvement in and resistance to the adoption of anti-discrimination legislation and even note that this institution, whether intentionally or unintentionally, often spreads anti-European and pro-Russian propaganda (Tsuladze, Esebua and Osepashvili 2021).

As noted above, there is a single Eurosceptic factor revealed by the research. It is hard to trace any trend in terms of its age and regional composition, which points to the fact that Eurosceptics are present in each age group and region. The participants with Eurosceptic sentiments believe that Georgia does not need to be taught tolerance by the EU and that the

Georgian government should not follow EU regulations regarding the protection of the rights of sexual minorities. In addition, they doubt Georgian products will be able to establish on the European market, and as the follow-up discussion reveals, this is ascribed to the EU's double standards, formally accepting but informally blocking Georgian products. Special attention should be paid to the statements occupying a negative pole as they once again confirm the Eurosceptic character of this factor: The role of the EU as a "teacher" for Georgia is negatively assessed, likewise the perspective of better protection of human rights alongside Georgia's European integration. However, it should be noted that the Eurosceptic position is not really related to the perceived identity threats, as the participants do not expect a harmful effect of European values on Georgian traditions. Furthermore, they do not consider European integration a threat to the country's sovereignty. It can be argued that the Eurosceptic position is mainly linked to the positive stance towards Russia, as confirmed by the highest positive value of the statement on the necessity of maintaining friendly relations with Russia within the Eurosceptic factor.

To summarize the main trends revealed based on the focus groups with citizens, it is obvious that Euro-optimistic views primarily based on pragmatic expectations prevail. As for identity considerations, it is noteworthy that, at least at the rhetorical level, the EU is no longer perceived as a threat to Georgian traditions and identity. However, in contrast to younger participants, who view Europeanization as a process contributing to the reinforcement of Georgians' tolerance, older participants express certain reservations regarding the rights of sexual minorities, which remains one of the most sensitive themes for Georgians. In this context, it is also important to touch upon the perceptions of the Georgian Orthodox Church's role in the process of Europeanization, as this highly influential institution is characterized by an explicitly negative rhetoric towards sexual minorities. Although both younger and older participants avoid overtly criticizing the Georgian Orthodox Church, young people are more outspoken and point to its role in hindering the adoption of anti-discrimination law as well as in spreading anti-European propaganda. Regarding the importance of maintaining friendly relations with Russia alongside Georgia's European integration, it is considered unacceptable to younger participants and acceptable to older participants as well as the Eurosceptics of all ages, which confirms that there is a close link between Eurosceptic and pro-Russian attitudes. Finally, it is noteworthy that the representatives of both younger and older generations share the same view regarding Georgia's prospects of joining the EU as the main pragmatic gain stemming from the

country's Europeanization. They believe that if Georgia persistently implements EU reforms, one day it will inevitably be granted EU membership.

Finally, to compare the elites and citizens' views on Georgia's Europeanization, the population envisages the same benefits from European integration as the elites do, especially in terms of reinforcing the country's democracy and security. No identity threats stemming from Europeanization are envisaged by either elites or young people, though the EU's support of sexual minorities evokes certain reservations among those over 40. Intellectual elites and young people believe that the generation raised in the post-Soviet times is more supportive of Georgia's European integration than the one socialized in the Soviet times, though those over 40 do not share this position and believe that the older generation is as supportive of the country's European integration as the younger one. In line with intellectual elites, young people argue that no reforms would have been in place without the EU's pressure, which seems a rather sensitive topic for the ruling party representatives and hence subject to their discursive manipulation. In contrast to political elites and older participants, young people and especially intellectual elites view the Georgian Orthodox Church as an obstacle to the country's Europeanization. Furthermore, intellectual elites and young people oppose to Georgia's maintaining friendly relations with Russia alongside the country's European integration, while the ruling party representatives avoid discussing this question and older participants openly state that "friendly" relations with Russia are necessary in order to counterbalance its power with clever manoeuvring. The question that both elites and citizens agree on is that the EU will ultimately reward Georgia's persistent attempts through granting it EU membership. Based on Q analysis, there is a close correlation among Factors "Politician", "NGO 2" and "Those under 40" that share their major pragmatic and identity considerations on Georgia's Europeanization. However, while further scrutinizing these factors, we find out that NGO representatives' and young people's assessments stand much closer to each other, displaying certain difference from those of politicians, and even more difference from those of the older generation.

Conclusion

Based on the Europeanization literature, there are two major factors – pragmatic and identity – that influence elites' and citizens' attitudes toward the EU. Studies show that both factors contribute to the formation of their respective attitudes in the old and new EU member states, though their prioritization is different. It has turned out that while the citizens of old member states expect immediate economic gains from European integration, those of new member

states anticipate better functioning of democratic institutions and reinforcement of their countries' security. The present paper demonstrates that Georgians' views closely resonate with those of their counterparts from the Eastern enlargement countries. Similar to the latter, Georgians' Euro-optimistic views are primarily caused by the pragmatic expectations regarding the EU's role in the strengthening of human rights protection, as well as the safeguarding of the country's security. Q analysis has confirmed that these are elites' and citizens' key arguments for legitimizing Georgia's European integration and justifying the necessity for adopting "painful" EU standards. Besides the pragmatic factors related to security and democracy matters, identity considerations also positively contribute to the perceptions of Georgia's Europeanization. No perceived identity threats stemming from the country's Europeanization are reported by either elites or citizens. Moreover, both groups underline the values shared by Georgians and Europeans, and even refer to Georgians' European identity.

However, in contrast to the Eastern enlargement countries, where research has revealed a shift from the initial Euro-optimistic discourse to a more pragmatic, Euro-realistic one, the current paper illustrates that Euro-optimism and pragmatism are closely intertwined in Georgian elites' and citizens' views. Moreover, it is the anticipation of pragmatic gains that encourages optimistic perceptions of the country's European integration and Europeanization. However, the research also shows that Euro-optimistic views might go hand in hand with the abovementioned "integration dilemma" characteristic of small and marginal countries like Georgia. They might fear certain transformations caused by the Europeanization process, such as the impact of strengthening the rights of sexual minorities on the local reality. Nevertheless, Euro-optimistic stance prevails even in such cases. As demonstrated by the presented elite and popular discourses, both pragmatic and identity factors are discursively used for the legitimization of Georgia's European integration and Europeanization.

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